

Aphanamixol, A Diterpene Alcohol from *Aphanamixis polystachya* (Wall) Parker*

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A neutral crystalline compound designated as aphanamixol, $C_{20}H_{36}O_2$, m.p. 130° , $[\alpha]_D^{25} -11^\circ$, isolated from the leaves of *Aphanamixis polystachya* (Wall) Parker, is shown to be a diterpenoid of manoyloxideseries from the studies of its spectroscopic data and other physical and chemical properties.

Aphanamixis polystachya (Wall) Parker (Synon : *Amoora rohituka*, N. O. *Meliaceae*) is a useful timber tree in Bengal. Its seeds, bark and leaves are used in the classical system of Indian medicine. Recently a tetracyclic triterpene, aphanamixin¹ has been isolated from the fruit-shell of the same plant which may be regarded as the direct biological precursor of tetranortriterpenoid furans produced by a large number of meliaceous plants.² From the leaves of *A. polystachya* two crystalline neutral compounds, namely, β -sitosterol, and aphanamixol have been isolated. During the later part of the study of aphanamixol, the isolation of the same substance was reported by Jefferies and his coworkers³ from the leaves of *Beyeria* species (N. O. *Euphorbiaceae*). These authors designated this compound as eperu-13-en-8 β :15 diol (Ic). We wish to report evidences leading to the same structure for this compound by degradative studies not reported by them.

Petroleum ether extract of the leaves upon chromatographic resolution over neutral alumina using chloroform as the eluent yielded aphanamixol. It has the molecular formula $C_{20}H_{36}O_2$ (M^+ 308), m.p. 130° , and $(\alpha)_D^{25} -11^\circ$. The compound showed the absence of phenolic, methoxyl and carbonyl groups from spectral and chemical data. The infrared spectrum provides several important information regarding the functionalities of aphanamixol. The presence of hydroxyl unsaturation, tertiary C-methyl and gem-dimethyl groups is revealed from the appearance of bands at 3300, 1666, 1408 and 1380 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum. The positive tetranitromethane colour reaction indicates the presence of at least one double bond, which is in consonance with the IR data (ν_{max} 1666 cm^{-1}); but this is not present as a vinylidene group (no formaldehyde upon ozonolysis). On catalytic hydrogenation it absorbed one mole of hydrogen yielding dihydroaphanamixol, $C_{20}H_{38}O_2$, m.p. $70-72^\circ$, thereby confirming the presence of a reducible double bond in the molecule.

Since Zerewitinoff determination gave 1.7 active hydrogen per molecule, it seemed probable that the two oxygen atoms were present as hydroxyl groups which were in accord with a broad band at 3300 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum. Attempted acetylation of aphanamixol

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1. A Chatterjee and Amit B. Kundu; *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1967, No. 16, 1471.

2. T. Chakraborty, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1966, 25, 544.

3. P. R. Jefferies and T. G. Payne, *Aus. J. Chem.*, 1965, 18, 1441.

under mild conditions led to the recovery of the starting material. But on heating with acetic anhydride and pyridine at 140-150° for 5 hrs., aphanamixol (Ia) underwent dehydration leading to a thick colourless liquid product (II). The IR absorption spectrum showed a sharp band at 3500 cm⁻¹ (hydroxyl) and a band of low intensity at 895 cm⁻¹ due to vinylidene group, the presence of which has further been confirmed by the formation of formaldehyde upon ozonolysis.

Additional information about the hydroxyl groups were obtained by oxidative experiments. Aphanamixol on oxidation with CrO₃/pyridine gave a semi-solid mass (IV) which failed to crystallise from any common organic solvent. It reduced ammoniacal silver nitrate solution and formed a 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 100-5°. The IR spectrum of the oxidation product which retained all the carbon atoms of the parent compound, as evidenced from the analysis of its DNPH, showed in addition to its hydroxyl band, a peak at 2750 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of a conjugated aldehydic function ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EIOH}}$ 235 mμ, log ε 3.84 ; ν_{max} 1710 cm⁻¹).

Aphanamixol on ozonolysis formed a thick, yellow-coloured, non-volatile substance (III) and glycollic aldehyde, m.p. 96°, characterised as its 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 183°. The non-volatile fraction responded to positive iodoform reaction suggesting thereby the presence of ketomethyl group in this product. Its UV and IR spectra showed the presence of a non-conjugated carbonyl function and for the keto methyl group the characteristic absorption peak in the IR spectrum was discernible at 1720 and 1356 cm⁻¹. All these evidences demonstrated the presence of the grouping CH₃ in aphanamixol (Ib) as shown below :

The empirical formula requires a total of three double bond equivalents. As one ethylenic double bond and two hydroxyl groups are presumed, the remaining two double bond equivalents are disposed for the bicyclic carbon skeleton. The fragmentation pattern as obtained by mass spectral studies suggests a close relationship to manoyl oxide derivative, the details of which will be reported elsewhere. In this connection the isolation of two phenolic diterpenoids viz. nimbiol (Id) and sugiol (Ie) from the bark of *Melia azadirachta* Linn⁴ (N.O. *Meliaceae*) needs mention which are also biogenetically related to manoyl. Thus all the information so far available regarding the structure of aphanamixol can be summarised by the expression (Ic).

4. P. Sengupta, S. N. Choudhuri and H. N. Khastgir, *Tetrahedron*, 1960, **10**, 45-54.

Attempted acetylation of aphanamixol. Aphanamixol (100 mg) was refluxed with a mixture of acetic anhydride (5 ml) and pyridine (2 ml) in an oil bath at 150° for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was then poured into crushed ice, extracted with ether, the ether extract repeatedly washed with water and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The ether on evaporation gave an oily mass which was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. On elution with petrol, a colourless oil (60 mg) was obtained. The oil was purified by distillation under reduced pressure (2 mm) when a thick colourless liquid (II) at 130° was collected; ν_{\max} 3500, 895 cm⁻¹; % Acetyl—nil.

Ozonolysis of II. To II (70 mg), dissolved in acetic acid (10 ml), a stream of ozonised oxygen was passed for 30-45 mins. The volatile fragments was collected in a flask containing dimedone solution when a precipitate was formed. The product was filtered and crystallised from alcohol when crystalline substance, m.p. 185° was obtained. It was found to be identical with an authentic formaldehyde-dimedone adduct (m.m.p.).

Catalytic hydrogenation of aphanamixol. To the sample (about 100 mg) dissolved in alcohol (10 ml), Pd/C (10%, 75 mg) was added and then hydrogenated for 10 hr. The substance absorbed 1 mole equivalent of hydrogen. After the reaction, the ethanol was evaporated and the thick oil (80 mg) was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina (2 gm). The benzene eluent on evaporation yielded a solid (60 mg), m.p. 55°. It was crystallised from aqueous methanol in colourless crystals, m.p. 70-72°; ν_{\max} 3500 cm⁻¹. (Found: C, 77.40; H, 12.20 and O, 10.4. C₂₀H₃₈O₂ requires: C, 77.42; H, 12.25 and O, 10.33%).

Sarrett oxidation of aphanamixol. Anhydrous CrO₃ (300 mg) was added to pyridine (5.5 ml) till brown precipitate due to the formation of pyridine complex appeared. Aphanamixol (350 mg) dissolved in minimum volume of pyridine was added to the pyridine complex and the reaction mixture was cooled below 0°. It was left overnight, decomposed with water and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The concentrated ether extract on chromatography gave a thick liquid product (IV) upon elution with benzene. The liquid was purified by distillation under reduced pressure (2 mm), b.p. 150° (yield 65 mg); $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 235 m μ ; log ϵ 4.33; ν_{\max} 3500, 2750, 1710 cm⁻¹; 2:4 dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 100-05° (Found: C, 63.98; H, 7.57; O, 16.98 and N, 11.30%. Calculated for C₂₆H₃₈O₅N₄: C, 64.19; H, 7.8; O, 16.46 and N, 11.52%).

Ozonolysis of aphanamixol. Aphanamixol (250 mg) dissolved in acetic acid (20 ml) was subjected to ozonolysis as described before; no volatile compounds could be detected. The reaction mixture was decomposed with Mg turnings and dilute HCl and kept overnight. Small amount of gummy solid that appeared was filtered and was identified as glycollic aldehyde, m.p. 96°; 2:4 dinitrophenyl hydrazone, m.p. 183-84°. It was found to be identical with an authentic 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of glycollic aldehyde (m.m.p.). The filtrate was extracted with CHCl₃, washed with water and dried. On evaporation of the solvent it yielded a thick liquid mass (200 mg) which failed to solidify even upon chromatographic resolution over neutral alumina; $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 280 m μ , log 4.80; ν_{\max} 1720 and 1356 cm⁻¹; iodoform, m.p. 119°.

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